

Evaluate the Efficacy, Safety and Tolerability of Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Versus Teneligliptin 20 mg in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus on Metformin Monotherapy

Preshita Prakash Vanjare^{1*}, Surbhi Jangir², Rakesh Sharma², Divya Singh²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Pharmacology, Jaipur College of Pharmacy, Jaipur, Rajasthan

²Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Jaipur College of Pharmacy, Jaipur, Rajasthan

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Corresponding author: Preshita Prakash Vanjare

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Abstract:

The study was a phase III, prospective, randomized, double blind, comparative, parallel group clinical study. The study screened 213 male and female patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus inadequately controlled on Metformin monotherapy, out of which 192 patients were randomized. Thus, 96 patients were randomized in test product i.e., Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets out of which 94 patients completed the study and 96 patients were randomized in reference product i.e. Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets out of which 93 patients completed the study.

The glycosylated hemoglobin was decreased in both the treatment groups. The difference in the mean change in glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) at the end of 16 weeks in the two groups was -0.03 with lower limit of 95% CI being -0.18. Thus, the results of the study show that Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets is non-inferior to Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets. All the treatments were well tolerated.

A total of 28 AEs were reported in 28 patients. 13 AEs were reported in Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets arm and 15 AEs were reported in Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets arm. 01 AE from Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets arm and 01 AE Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets arm were moderate in nature; all the other AEs were mild in nature. No SAE was reported during the study.

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Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by persistent hyperglycaemia. It may be due to impaired insulin secretion, resistance to peripheral actions of insulin, or both. Chronic hyperglycaemia in synergy with the other metabolic aberrations in diabetic patients can cause damage to various organ systems, leading to the development of disabling and life-threatening health complications, most prominent of which are microvascular (retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy) and macrovascular complications leading to a 2-fold to a 4-fold increased risk of cardiovascular diseases. [1]

The main symptoms are:

Polyuria (frequent urination) Polydipsia (increased thirst) Polyphagia (increased hunger) Weakness Weight loss and loss of muscle bulk frequent episodes of thrush Cuts or wounds that heal slowly Blurred vision [2] DM is broadly classified into 3 types by etiology and clinical presentation, type 1 diabetes, type 2 diabetes, and gestational diabetes (GDM). Some other less common types of diabetes

include monogenic diabetes and secondary diabetes.

Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (T1DM): Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) accounts for 5% to 10% of DM and is characterized by autoimmune destruction of insulin-producing beta cells in the islets of the pancreas. As a result, there is an absolute deficiency of insulin. A combination of genetic susceptibility and environmental factors such as viral infection, toxins, or some dietary factors has been implicated as triggers for autoimmunity. T1DM is most commonly seen in children and adolescents though it can develop at any age.

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM)

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) accounts for around 90% of all cases of diabetes. In T2DM, the response to insulin is diminished, and this is defined as insulin resistance. During this state, insulin is ineffective and is initially countered by an increase in insulin production to maintain glucose homeostasis, but over time, insulin production decreases resulting in T2DM. T2DM is most

commonly seen in persons older than 45 years, but it is increasingly seen in children, adolescents, and younger adults due to rising levels of obesity, physical inactivity, and energy-dense diets.

Gestational Diabetes Mellitus

Hyperglycaemia which is first detected during pregnancy is classified as gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), also known as hyperglycaemia in pregnancy. Although it can occur anytime during pregnancy, GDM generally affects pregnant women during the second and third trimesters. According to American Diabetes Association (ADA), GDM complicates 7% of all pregnancies. Women with GDM and their offspring have an increased risk of developing type 2 diabetes mellitus in the future. GDM can be complicated by hypertension, preeclampsia, and hydramnios and may also lead to increased operative interventions. The foetus can have increased weight and size (macrosomia) or congenital anomalies. Even after birth, such infants may have respiratory distress syndrome, and subsequent childhood and adolescent obesity. Older age, obesity, excessive gestational weight gain, history of congenital anomalies in previous children, or stillbirth, or a family history of diabetes are risk factors for GDM.

Monogenic Diabetes: A single genetic mutation in an autosomal dominant gene causes this type of diabetes. Examples of monogenic diabetes include conditions like neonatal diabetes mellitus and maturity-onset diabetes of the young (MODY). Around 1% to 5% of all diabetes cases are due to monogenic diabetes. MODY is familial disorder and usually presents under age of 25 years.

Secondary Diabetes: Secondary diabetes is caused due to the complication of other diseases affecting pancreas (for example, pancreatitis), hormone disturbances (for example, Cushing's disease), or due to drugs (for example, corticosteroids). [1]

Epidemiology: Diabetes is a worldwide epidemic. With changing lifestyle and increasing obesity, the prevalence of DM has increased worldwide. The worldwide prevalence of DM was 425 million in 2017. According to International Diabetes Federation (IDF), in 2015, about 10% of the American population had diabetes. Of these, 7 million were undiagnosed. With an increase in age, the prevalence of DM also increases. About 25% of the population above 65 years of age has diabetes. [1]

Diabetes is a growing challenge in India with estimated 8.7% diabetic population in the age group of 20 and 70 years. The rising prevalence of diabetes and other noncommunicable diseases is driven by a combination of factors - rapid

urbanization, sedentary lifestyles, unhealthy diets, tobacco use, and increasing life expectancy. [3]

Over 30 million have now been diagnosed with diabetes in India. The CPR (Crude prevalence rate) in the urban areas of India is thought to be 9 per cent. In rural areas, the prevalence is approximately 3 per cent of the total population. The population of India is now more than 1000 million: this helps to give an idea of the scale of the problem. The estimate of the actual number of diabetics in India is around 40 million. This means that India actually has the highest number of diabetics of any one country in the entire world. IGT (Impaired Glucose Tolerance) is also a mounting problem in India. The prevalence of IGT is thought to be around

8.7 per cent in urban areas and 7.9 per cent in rural areas, although this estimate may be too high. It is thought that around 35 per cent of IGT sufferers go on to develop type 2 diabetes, so India is genuinely facing a healthcare crisis. In India, the type of diabetes differs considerably from that in the Western world. [4]

Pathophysiology: T2DM is an insulin-resistance condition with associated beta cell dysfunction. Initially, there is a compensatory increase in insulin secretion which maintains glucose levels in normal range. As the condition progresses, beta cells change, and the insulin secretion is unable to maintain glucose homeostasis, producing hyperglycaemia. Most of the patients with T2DM are obese or have higher body fat percentage, distributed predominantly in the abdominal region. This adipose tissue itself promotes insulin resistance through various inflammatory mechanisms including increased FFA (free fatty acids) release and adipokine dysregulation. Lack of physical activity, prior GDM in those with hypertension, or dyslipidaemia also increase the risk of developing T2DM. Evolving data suggest a role for adipokine dysregulation, inflammation, abnormal incretin biology with decreased incretins such as glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) or incretin resistance, hyperglucagonemia, increased renal glucose reabsorption and abnormalities in gut microbiota. [1]

Diagnosis: The clinical diagnosis of diabetics is often prompted by symptoms such as increased thirst and urination and recurrent infections.

Blood Tests - Fasting plasma glucose, two-hour postprandial test and oral glucose tolerance test are done to know blood glucose levels.

Glycated Haemoglobin (HbA1c) may be used to diagnose diabetes. [2] Diagnostic criteria for diabetes and prediabetes: [5]

Table 1: Parameter

Parameter	Normoglycemia	Prediabetes	Diabetes
FPG	< 110 mg/dL	110-125 mg/dL (IFG)	≥ 126 mg/dL
2-h PG	< 140 mg/dL	140-199 mg/dL (IGT)	≥ 200 mg/dL
HbA1c	<5.7%	5.7-6.4%	≥ 6.5%
Random plasmagluco ^s *			≥ 200 mg/dL (with symptoms of diabetes)

*Individuals with random plasma glucose between 140-199 mg/dl are recommended to undergo OGTT. IFG - Impaired Fasting Glucose; IGT - Impaired Glucose tolerance; FPG - Fasting Plasma Glucose; 2-h PG - 2 hour post load Glucose test (oral glucose tolerance test) plasma glucose. HbA1c – Glycosylated Haemoglobin.[5]

Management

Through lifestyle and diet modification. Studies have shown that there was significant reduction in the incidence of type 2 DM with a combination

of maintenance of body mass index of 25 kg/m², eating high fibre and unsaturated fat and diet low in saturated and trans-fats and glycaemic index, regular exercise, abstinence from smoking and moderate consumption of alcohol. Suggesting that majority of type 2 DM can be prevented by lifestyle modification. Patients with type 2 DM should receive a medical nutrition evaluation;

lifestyle recommendations should be tailored according to physical and functional ability. [6]

Treatment:

Figure 1: Mechanism of action of Anti-Hyperglycaemic drugs

SU- Sulfonylureas; DPP4i- Dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitors (Gliptins); GLP-1RA- Glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists; TZD- Thiazolidinediones (Glitazones); AGI- Alpha-glucosidase inhibitor; Glinide- Non- sulphonyl urea insulin secretagogue (Repaglinide and

Nateglinide); SGLT2i- Sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitor⁵

Study Design

This trial is a Phase IV, Prospective, Randomized, Comparative, Parallel Group, Clinical Study to

Evaluate the Efficacy, Safety and Tolerability of Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Versus Tenzeligiptin 20 mg in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.

After confirming the inclusion/exclusion criteria the subject will be randomized and provided with study medication at randomization visit. Subjects will be provided with diary at randomization visit,

which need to be brought along with in each subsequent visit till the last visit.

Follow up visits will be done on week 2/day 14(±3), week 6/day 42(±3), week 12/day 84(±3) and week 16/day 112(±3) (Final Visit) of treatment to assess efficacy, safety and tolerability.

Figure 2: flow chart

Table 2:

Total Number of Subject Visits	6
Treatment Duration	16 weeks
Type of Randomization	Block Randomization

Subject Eligibility

Inclusion Criteria: Patients will be entered into this study only if they meet all the following criteria:

1. Male or Female Patients aged between 18 to 65 (both inclusive) years with diagnosis of Type 2 diabetes mellitus.
2. Patients who have received stable dose of Metformin ≥ 1500 mg/day as monotherapy for at least 3 months prior to screening and having inadequate glycemic control at screening defined as HbA1c levels of ≥ 8.0% to ≤ 9.5%.
3. Women of childbearing potential (WOCBP) must be using an acceptable method of contraception to avoid pregnancy throughout the study. WOCBP must have a negative urine pregnancy test at screening / baseline visit.
4. Patient with ability to understand and provide written informed consent form, which must have been obtained prior to screening.
5. Patients willing to comply with the protocol requirements.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients that meet any of the following criteria must not be enrolled in the study:

1. Patients with a history of Type 1 diabetes mellitus or secondary diabetes mellitus or diabetes insipidus.
2. Patients with a history of metabolic acidosis or diabetic ketoacidosis.
3. Patients with a history of bariatric surgery or lap-band procedure within 12 months prior to screening.
4. Patients with Fasting Plasma Glucose (FPG) > 270 mg/dL at screening (If FPG is > 270 mg/dL at screening, FPG will be repeated within 1 week. If repeat FPG is > 270 mg/dL, patient will be excluded from the study).
5. Patients with the Body Mass Index (BMI) \geq 45.0 kg/m² at screening.
6. Patients with Estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) <60 mL/min/1.73 m² [using the Modification of Diet in Renal Disease (MDRD) equation] at screening.
7. Patients with clinically significant impaired hepatic function (SGOT & SGPT more than 3X the UNL and/or Total bilirubin more than 1.5X the UNL) at screening.
8. Patients with a history of congestive heart failure defined as New York Heart Association (NYHA) class III/IV, unstable or acute congestive heart failure.
9. Patients with significant cardiovascular history defined as: myocardial infarction, unstable angina pectoris, transient ischemic attack, unstable or previously undiagnosed arrhythmia, cardiac surgery or revascularization (coronary angioplasty or bypass grafts), or cerebrovascular accident.
10. Patients with uncontrolled hypertension with sitting systolic BP \geq 160 mmHg and/or diastolic BP \geq 100 mmHg at screening.
11. Any abnormality on 12-lead ECG at screening that in the opinion of the investigator is clinically significant and is judged as potential risk for patient's participation in the study.
12. Patients with history of hereditary QT prolongation syndrome or patients having history of Torsades de pointes.
13. Patients who are accepting treatments of arrhythmias.
14. Patients with a history of anaemia or hemoglobinopathy and/or haemoglobin < 10 g/dL for men; haemoglobin < 9 g/dL for women at screening.
15. Patients with known history of acute pancreatitis.
16. Patients with a history of treatment with estrogens and other medications known to affect bone.
17. Patients with history of clinically significant peripheral edema in past 6 months.
18. Patients with intolerance, contraindication or potential allergy/hypersensitivity to any of the ingredients of study medication or any other DPP4 inhibitors or Thiazolidinediones.
19. Pregnant or breast-feeding or expecting to conceive within the projected duration of the study.
20. Female patients who are of childbearing potential and who are neither surgically sterilized nor willing to use reliable contraceptive methods (like hormonal, barrier methods or intrauterine device).
21. Patients with history of any malignancy.
22. Patients with known case of infection with hepatitis B, hepatitis C or HIV.
23. Patients with donation or transfusion of blood, plasma, or platelets within the past 3 months prior to screening.
24. Patients with a history of substance abuse or dependence that in the opinion of the Investigator is considered to interfere with the patient's participation in the study.
25. Patients with concurrent participation in another clinical trial or any investigational therapy within 30 days prior to signing informed consent.
26. Patients currently taking any of the prohibited medications(s) and inability/unwillingness to discontinue them for the entire study period.
27. Suspected inability or unwillingness to comply with the study procedures.
28. Patient with any condition which, in the judgment of the Investigator, may render the patient unable to complete the study or which may pose a significant risk to the patient.

Discontinuation/Withdrawal Criteria:

In accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and other applicable regulations, a subject has the right to withdraw consent for participating in the study at any time and for any reason without prejudice to his or her future medical care by the physician or at the institution.

Patients may be withdrawn entirely from the study for the following reasons:

Patients will be allowed to withdraw from the study anytime without stating the reason. However, every attempt will be made by the investigator to find out and record the reason. Also, patients will be explained the risks of sudden cessation of therapy. Conversely, if the investigator feels appropriate, he/she may withdraw the patient from the study and reasons for the same should be documented properly.

It will be documented whether each patient completed each study phase or not. If the study treatment or observations were discontinued for

any patients, the reason will be recorded. Reason for the discontinuation of study treatment by patient may be one of the following:

1. Patients at their own request voluntarily or at the request of their legally acceptable representative can be withdrawn from the study.
2. Any clinical adverse event (AE), laboratory abnormality or intercurrent illness which, in the opinion of the investigator, indicates that continued participation in the study is not in the best interest of the patient.
3. If a concomitant therapy is reported or required which is liable to interfere with the result of the study.
4. If at any point of the study patient is found to be non-compliant with the study protocol.
5. Patients who become pregnant during the study period.

Any female subject who has a positive pregnancy test after signing informed consent should be withdrawn from the study immediately and study medication should be discontinued immediately.

Note: Patient withdrawn from the study from either arm will be provided standard care of treatment.

Non-compliant with the study protocol

- If the patient misses ≥ 7 consecutive doses of the study medication.
- Patients are using any prohibited medication during the study.
- There is an indication that a patient has not agreed with or followed the instructions related to the study medication.
- Patient has not agreed for the blood collection for laboratory assessment.

In all cases, the reason for withdrawal or cases of drop out must be recorded in subject's source documents and case report forms by the investigator. If the reason for subject withdrawal is not known, subject must be followed for the proper reason. All possible attempts will be made for the follow-up of all the subjects who miss a study follow-up visit. In case of any exacerbations of disease or treatment failure, study medication will be discontinued and alternative therapy will be provided as decided by the investigator.

The investigator will also complete the end of study/early termination procedures before termination and will classify the termination status of each subject at the end of study in the end of visit page in source documents and case report form as well. The discontinued subject due to AEs will be followed up till it gets resolved.

Discontinuation guidelines for protocol-defined severe hypoglycaemia episodes or recurrent non-severe hypoglycaemia episodes

Patients will be recommended to continue on the study and not discontinue from treatment based on single episodes of hypoglycaemia or symptoms of hypoglycaemia unless clinically indicated. The assessment of a single finger stick or laboratory glucose value should not be the sole assessment used to determine patient discontinuation for hypoglycaemia.

Clinical indications for discontinuation because of hypoglycaemia should include the following:

a) Multiple occasions of episodes outlined below that, in the opinion of the Investigator, indicate that continued treatment with study therapy is not in the best interest of the patient. This includes, but is not limited to: Symptoms suggestive of hypoglycaemia (e.g., sweating, shakiness, increased heart rate, confusion, dizziness, light-headedness, or hunger) in the absence of environmental factors known to contribute to hypoglycaemia (i.e., excess physical activity, concurrent illness, or missed or delayed meal) and/or Documented finger stick glucose values $< 54\text{mg/dL}$ ($< 3.0\text{mmol/L}$)

b) A patient may also be discontinued from the study because of severe hypoglycaemia, as determined by the Investigator.

Major episode: defines as a symptomatic episode requiring external (3rd party) assistance due to severe impairment in consciousness or behavior with a glucose value $< 54\text{ mg/dL}$ and prompt recovery after glucose or glucagon administration.

Minor episode: defined as either a symptomatic episode with a capillary or plasma glucose measurement $< 63\text{ mg/dL}$, regardless of need for external assistance, or an asymptomatic capillary or plasma glucose measurement $< 63\text{ mg/dL}$ that does not qualify as a major episode

Other episode: defined as suggestive episode reported but not meeting the criteria for major or minor episodes

Procedures for discontinuation of a patient from investigational product

At any time, patients are free to discontinue IP or withdraw from the study (i.e., IP and assessments), without prejudice to further treatment. A patient who decides to discontinue IP will always be asked about the reason(s) and the presence of any AEs. If possible, the patient will be seen and assessed by an Investigator. Any AEs will be followed up; diary and all study drugs should be returned by the patient.

Patients who discontinue from the study medication will have an Early Termination Visit equivalent to

the Visit 6 (Week 16 / End of Treatment) assessments immediately following discontinuation of study medication. If a patient is discontinued from the study, his/her randomization or enrolment number will not be reused, and the patient will not be allowed to re-enter the study. Randomised patients who discontinue early from the study will not be replaced.

In all cases, the reason for withdrawal or cases of drop out must be recorded in subject's source documents and case report forms by the investigator. If the reason for subject withdrawal is not known, subject must be followed for the proper reason. All possible attempts will be made for the follow-up of all the subjects who miss a study follow-up visit. In case of any exacerbations of disease or treatment failure, study medication will be discontinued and alternative therapy will be provided as decided by the investigator.

The investigator will also complete the end of study/early termination procedures before termination and will classify the termination status of each subject at the end of study in the end of visit page in source documents and case report form as well. The discontinued subject due to AEs will be followed up till it gets resolved.

Lost to Follow-up

A subject will be considered lost-to-follow-up only if no contact has been established by the time study is completed such that there is insufficient information to determine the subject's status on follow-up visit (Visit 6). Subjects refusing to return to the site or to continue participation in the study should be documented as "withdrawal of consent" rather than "lost to follow-up".

Investigators should document attempts to re-establish contact with missing subjects throughout the study period. If contact with a missing subject is re-established, the subject should not be considered lost-to-follow-up and any evaluations should resume according to the protocol.

Permanent Discontinuation of Study Drug

A subject who is permanently discontinued from further receipt of study drug, regardless of the reason (withdrawal of consent, due to an AE, other), will be identified as having permanently

discontinued treatment.

Replacement of Subjects: Discontinued subjects will not be replaced.

Study Population: A total of 86 evaluable patients in each treatment group is estimated to provide a power of 90% at one sided significance level of 2.5% (2 sided 5%), with assumed standard deviation of 1.0% of HbA1c, to demonstrate non-inferiority of Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets in comparison with Teneligliptin 20 mg in HbA1c change from baseline to week 16, with a non-inferiority margin (Δ) of 0.40. Assuming a mean difference of 0.1% in HbA1c between Vildagliptin SR 100 mg and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets. Total 172 evaluable patients will be considered for this study.

- 86 Patients in Vildagliptin SR 100 mg
- 86 Patients in Teneligliptin 20 mg

Sufficient number of patients will be enrolled to get 172 evaluable patients for completing 16 weeks of treatment.

Study Assessment

Primary Efficacy End Point:

- Mean change in glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks).
- Secondary Efficacy End Points:
- Mean change in fasting plasma glucose (FPG) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks).
- Proportion of patients achieving a therapeutic glycaemic response, defined as HbA1c < 7% at the end of the study visit (16 weeks).
- Mean change in body weight from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks).
- Safety End Points:
- Hypoglycemic episodes during the study.
- Adverse events reported during the study.
- Serious adverse events reported during the study.
- Changes in clinical laboratory parameters from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks).

Study Procedures

Study Schedule

Table 3: Study Procedures

Study Procedures	Visit 1 (Screening / Baseline) Day -7	Visit 2 (Randomization) Day 1	Visit 3 (Follow up visit) Week 2 / Day 14 (± 3)	Visit 4 (Follow up visit) Week 6/ Day 42 (± 3)	Visit 5 (Follow up visit) Week 12 / Day 84 (± 3)	Visit 6 (End of the study visit) Week 16 / Day 112 (± 3)
Written Informed consent form	X	-	-	-	-	-
Demography	X	-	-	-	-	-
Medical & Surgical history	X	-	-	-	-	-
Vital Signs measurement	X	X	X	X	X	X
Body weight & BMI	X	-	X	X	X	X
Physical Examination	X	X	X	X	X	X
COVID-19 signs & symptoms	X	X	X	X	X	X
Verification of Concomitant medications	X	X	X	X	X	X
Urine pregnancy test	X	-	-	X	X	X
HbA1c measurement	X	-	-	-	X	X
FPG measurement	X	-	X	X	X	X
Inclusion / Exclusion criteria	X	-	-	-	-	-
Inclusion / Exclusion criteria verification	-	X	-	-	-	-
Patient randomization	-	X	-	-	-	-
Study medication dispensing	-	X	X	X	X	-
Study medication return	-	-	X	X	X	X
Study medication compliance check	-	-	X	X	X	X
AE and SAE assessment	-	-	X	X	X	X
Hypoglycemic episodes assessment	-	-	X	X	X	X

Note: Vital signs include resting blood pressure, pulse rate, respiratory rate and oral temperature. Subjects should be instructed to self-monitor their blood glucose at least once weekly and at the occurrence of hypoglycaemia symptoms. Subjects should record blood glucose readings in the diary and report to the investigator in the event of usually high or low blood glucose.

Disposition of Patients

A total of 213 patients were screened out of which 192 patients were randomized in the study. 15

patients had screen failure and 06 patients were voluntarily consent withdrawn before randomization. Total 96 patients were randomized in Test product i.e., Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets out of which 94 patients completed the study and 96 patients were randomized in Reference product i.e., Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets out of which 93 patients completed the study. The following figure shows the summary of the patient disposition in the study. 15 Patients were screen failure and 05 patients were withdrew consent before randomization.

Figure 3: Patient Disposition Chart

Table 4: Overall Patient Disposition by Treatment Group - All Participants

	Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets N=96	Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets N=96	Total N=192
Total patients screened	--	--	213
Screen failure	--	--	15
Consent withdrawn before randomization	--	--	06
Eligible for randomization	96	96	192
Total randomized patients in the study	96	96	192
Completed patients	94	93	187
Not completed patients	02	03	05
Reason for early discontinuation			
Protocol violation	--	--	--
At the discretion of the investigator	--	--	--
Lack of efficacy	--	--	--
Adverse events	--	--	--
Disease progression/recurrence	--	--	--
Intercurrent illness that prevents further administration of treatment	--	--	--
Lost to follow up	02	03	05
Death	--	--	--
Change in the patient's condition rendering the patient unacceptable for further treatment in the judgment of the investigator	--	--	--

Efficacy Evaluation

A. Data Sets Analysed

The study was planned to obtain the data from all the evaluable patients. Out of 192 randomized patients 187 patients have completed the study. 05 patients were lost to follow up from the study. 96 patients were randomized in Test product arm i.e., Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets of which 94 patients have completed the study and 96 patients were randomized in Reference product arm i.e., Teneagliptin 20 mg Tablets of which 93 patients have completed the study.

B. Demographic and Other Baseline Characteristics

All patients were in the range of 18 to 65 years of age (both inclusive) as per protocol. Average body weight was comparable with an average of 63.94 kg in Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets arm and 63.94 kg in Teneagliptin 20 mg Tablets arm. All the patients in the study were Asian.

Table 4: Demographic Characteristics by Treatment Group

Characteristics	Statistics	Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets	Teneagliptin 20 mg Tablets	P-Value
Age (Year)	N	96	96	0.3249
	Mean (SD)	45.81 (9.46)	44.52 (8.66)	
	(Min, Max)	(26.00, 64.00)	(30.00, 63.00)	
Height (Cm)	N	96	96	0.5343
	Mean (SD)	163.85 (5.81)	163.29 (6.68)	
	(Min, Max)	(152.00, 178.00)	(148.00, 178.00)	
Weight (Kg)	N	96	96	0.9993
	Mean (SD)	63.94 (7.59)	63.94 (8.20)	
	(Min, Max)	(49.00, 86.00)	(47.00, 83.00)	
BMI (Kg/m ²)	N	96	96	0.6341
	Mean (SD)	23.77 (2.18)	23.93 (2.27)	
	(Min, Max)	(19.60, 31.20)	(19.70, 30.40)	
Sex	N	96	96	0.6646
	Male	47 (48.96%)	44 (45.83%)	
	Female	49 (51.04%)	52 (54.17%)	

Note:

For age, height, weight and BMI: P-value obtained using 2-sample t-test test between Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneagliptin 20 mg Tablets.

For Sex: P-value is calculated using Chi-square test.

C. Measurements of Treatment Compliance:
The measurement of treatment compliance is mentioned in the following tables.

Table 5: Outcomes Assessment Completeness by Treatment Group

Test and Visit	X1	X2	Total
	N=96	N=96	N=192
Efficacy Assessment			
Screening/Baseline Visit (Visit 1)	96	96	192
Randomization Visit (Day 1/Visit 2)	96	96	192
Follow up Visit (Week 2/Day 14±3) - Visit 3	96	96	192
Follow up Visit (Week 6/Day 42±3) - Visit 4	96	96	192
Follow up Visit (Week 12/Day 84±3) - Visit 5	96	95	191
End of the study Visit (Week 16/Day 112±3) - Visit 6	94	93	187
Safety Assessment			
Screening/Baseline Visit (Visit 1)	96	96	192
Randomization Visit (Day 1/Visit 2)	96	96	192
Follow up Visit (Week 2/Day 14±3) - Visit 3	96	96	192
Follow up Visit (Week 6/Day 42±3) - Visit 4	96	96	192
Follow up Visit (Week 12/Day 84±3) - Visit 5	96	95	191
End of the study Visit (Week 16/Day 112±3) - Visit 6	94	93	187

Note: X1 = Vildagliptin SR 100 mg, X2 = Teneagliptin 20 mg

D. Efficacy Results and Tabulations of Individual Patient Data

Analysis of Efficacy: Efficacy of the investigational product was analyzed based on mean change in glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks), mean change in fasting plasma glucose (FPG) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks), mean change in 2-hr post prandial plasma glucose (2-hr PPG) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks), proportion of patients achieving a therapeutic glycemic response, defined as HbA1c <

7% at the end of the study visit (16 weeks) and mean change in body weight from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks). As per the statistical analysis plan, the efficacy data was analyzed for effect on individual and cumulative efficacy parameter.

Primary Efficacy Endpoint: Mean change in glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks).

mITT analysis population

Table 6: Mean change in glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

Variable	Statistics	Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets (N=96)	Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets (N=96)
Mean change from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)	LSM (SE)	-1.5020 (0.05670)	-1.4719 (0.05670)
	95% CI	(-1.6135, -1.3905)	(-1.5834, -1.3604)
	Difference: LSM (SE)	-0.03012 (0.08019)	
	95% CI of difference	(-0.1878, 0.1276)	
	P-value	0.7074	

Note: HbA1c units = % & Last observation carried forward (LOCF) method was used for missing values

Difference: Least square mean (LSM) and standard error (SE) between groups calculated for Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets.

The 95% confidence intervals (CI) for the LSM mean difference in HbA1c (%) between groups are

calculated for Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets.

P-value is obtained using repeated measures analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) to compare mean change from baseline values of Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets.

Figure 4: Mean change in glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

PP analysis population

Table 7: Mean change in glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

Variable	Statistics	Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets (N=94)	Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets (N=93)
Mean change from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)	LSM (SE)	-1.5092 (0.05586)	-1.5025 (0.05616)
	95% CI	(-1.6190, -1.3994)	(-1.6130, -1.3921)
	Difference: LSM (SE)	-0.00666 (0.07921)	
	95% CI of difference	(-0.1624, 0.1491)	
	P-value	0.9331	

Note: HbA1c units = %

Difference: Least square mean (LSM) and standard error (SE) between groups calculated for Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets. The 95% confidence intervals (CI) for the LSM mean difference in HbA1c (%)

between groups are calculated for Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets. P-value is obtained using repeated measures analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) to compare mean change from baseline values of Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets.

Figure 5: Mean change in glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

Secondary Efficacy Endpoints: Mean change in fasting plasma glucose (FPG) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

mITT analysis population

Table 8: Mean change in fasting plasma glucose (FPG) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

Variable	Statistics	Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets (N=96)	Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets (N=96)
Mean change from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)	LSM (SE)	-40.3572 (1.4293)	-39.3091 (1.4293)
	95% CI	(-43.1645, -37.5498)	(-42.1164, -36.5018)
	Difference: LSM (SE)	-1.0481 (2.0215)	
	95% CI of difference	(-5.0186, 2.9225)	
	P-value	0.6044	

Note:

FPG units = mg/dL

Last observation carried forward (LOCF) method was used for missing values.

Difference: Least square mean (LSM) and standard error (SE) between groups calculated for Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets.

The 95% confidence intervals (CI) for the LSM mean difference in FPG (mg/dL) between groups

are calculated for Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets.

P-value is obtained using repeated measures analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) to compare mean change from baseline values of Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets.

Figure 6: Mean change in fasting plasma glucose (FPG) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

PP analysis population

Table 9: Mean change in fasting plasma glucose (FPG) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

Variable	Statistics	Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets (N=94)	Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets (N=93)
Mean change from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)	LSM (SE)	-40.8499 (1.4308)	-39.3017 (1.4385)
	95% CI	(-43.6603, -38.0395)	(-42.1272, -36.4762)
	Difference: LSM (SE)	-1.5482 (2.0294)	
	95% CI of difference	(-5.5344, 2.4379)	
	P-value	0.4458	

Note:

FPG units = mg/dL

Difference: Least square mean (LSM) and standard error (SE) between groups calculated for Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets. The 95% confidence intervals (CI)

for the LSM mean difference in FPG (mg/dL) between groups are calculated for Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets. P-value is obtained using repeated measures analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) to compare mean change from baseline values of Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets.

Figure 7: Mean change in fasting plasma glucose (FPG) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

Mean change in 2-hr post prandial plasma glucose (2-hr PPG) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

mITT analysis population

Table 10: Mean change in 2-hr post prandial plasma glucose (2-hr PPG) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

Variable	Statistics	Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets (N=96)	Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets (N=96)
Mean change from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)	LSM (SE)	-77.9637 (2.1976)	-77.0136 (2.1976)
	95% CI	(-82.2846, -73.6427)	(-81.3346, -72.6927)
	Difference: LSM (SE)	-0.9500 (3.1081)	
	95% CI of difference	(-7.0613, 5.1612)	
	P-value	0.7600	

Note:

2-hr PPG units = mg/dL

Last observation carried forward (LOCF) method was used for missing values.

Difference: Least square mean (LSM) and standard error (SE) between groups calculated for Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets.

The 95% confidence intervals (CI) for the LSM mean difference in 2-hr PPG (mg/dL) between groups are calculated for Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets.

P-value is obtained using repeated measures analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) to compare mean change from baseline values of Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets.

Figure 8: Mean change in 2-hr post prandial plasma glucose (2-hr PPG) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

PP analysis population

Table 11: Mean change in 2-hr post prandial plasma glucose (2-hr PPG) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

Variable	Statistics	Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets (N=94)	Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets (N=93)
Mean change from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)	LSM (SE)	-78.2448 (2.2108)	-77.5761 (2.2226)
	95% CI	(-82.5921, -73.8975)	(-81.9467, -73.2055)
	Difference: LSM (SE)	-0.6686 (3.1360)	
	95% CI of difference	(-6.8352, 5.4979)	
	P-value	0.8313	

Note:

2-hr PPG units = mg/dL

Difference: Least square mean (LSM) and standard error (SE) between groups calculated for Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets. The 95% confidence intervals (CI)

for the LSM mean difference in 2-hr PPG (mg/dL) between groups are calculated for Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets. P-value is obtained using repeated measures analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) to compare mean change from baseline values of Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets.

Figure 9: Mean change in 2-hr post prandial plasma glucose (2-hr PPG) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

Proportion of patients achieving a therapeutic glyceimic response, defined as HbA1c < 7% at the end of the study visit (16 weeks)

Table 12: Proportion of patients achieving a therapeutic glyceimic response, defined as HbA1c < 7% at the end of the study visit (16 weeks)

Visit	Statistics	Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets (N=96)	Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets (N=96)
Visit 6 / Day 112 (Week 16)	N (%)	42 (43.75%)	39 (40.63%)
P-Value		0.6611	

Note: P-value is obtained using Chi-square test.

Figure 10: Proportion of patients achieving a therapeutic glyceimic response, defined as HbA1c < 7% at the end of the study visit (16 weeks)

Mean change in body weight from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

mITT analysis population

Table 13: Mean change in body weight from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

Variable	Statistics	Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets (N=96)	Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets (N=96)
Mean change from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)	LSM (SE)	0.9563 (0.1075)	0.8896 (0.1075)
	95% CI	(0.7450, 1.1675)	(0.6783, 1.1008)
	Difference: LSM (SE)	0.06669 (0.1521)	
	95% CI of difference	(-0.2321, 0.3654)	
	P-value	0.6612	

Note:

Body weight units = kg

Last observation carried forward (LOCF) method was used for missing values.

Difference: Least square mean (LSM) and standard error (SE) between groups calculated for Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin

20 mg Tablets. The 95% confidence intervals (CI) for the LSM mean difference in body weight (kg) between groups are calculated for Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets.

P-value is obtained using repeated measures analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) to compare mean change from baseline values of Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets

Figure 11: Mean change in body weight from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

PP analysis population

Table 14: Mean change in body weight from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

Variable	Statistics	Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets (N=94)	Teneagliptin 20 mg Tablets (N=93)
Mean change from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)	LSM (SE)	0.9495 (0.1095)	0.8866 (0.1101)
	95% CI	(0.7344, 1.1645)	(0.6704, 1.1027)
	Difference: LSM (SE)	0.06292 (0.1552)	
	95% CI of difference	(-0.2420, 0.3679)	
	P-value	0.6854	

Note:

Body weight units = kg

Difference: Least square mean (LSM) and standard error (SE) between groups calculated for Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneagliptin 20 mg Tablets. The 95% confidence intervals (CI)

for the LSM mean difference in body weight (kg) between groups are calculated for Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneagliptin 20 mg Tablets. P-value is obtained using repeated measures analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) to compare mean change from baseline values of Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneagliptin 20 mg Tablets

Figure 12: Mean change in body weight from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks)

Efficacy Conclusions

Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets produced statistically significant reductions in glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c), fasting plasma glucose (FPG) and 2-hour post prandial plasma glucose (2-hr PPG) from baseline to end of the study visit. No significant differences were observed between Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus inadequately controlled on Metformin monotherapy.

For primary efficacy variable, mean change in glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks) in the two groups has been calculated and non-inferiority has been considered when the lower bound of the two-sided 95% CI of the difference between the mean change in glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) at week 16 as compared to baseline (Test product – Reference product) is not less than -0.40. The glycosylated hemoglobin was decreased in both the treatment groups. The difference in the mean change in glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) at the end of 16 weeks in the two groups was -0.03 with lower limit of 95% CI being -0.18, thereby meeting the requirements of non-inferiority criteria. Thus, the results of the study show that Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets is non-inferior to Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets.

Safety Population

Adverse events were coded using the Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities (MedDRA) version no. 23.0. Frequency of AEs was calculated for each system organ class and preferred term by treatment group. The number of patients and proportion reporting each AE was summarized. The severity of the AE and relationship to study medication was summarized for each system organ class and preferred term by treatment group.

Self-reported and elicited reports of adverse events, changes in concomitant therapy and mortality are presented in listings and summarized in tables. All patients with complication of therapy were described and analysed to ascertain relationships, if any, to study centre and patient using appropriate descriptive statistics, continuous variables were summarized using number of observations, mean, SD, minimum and maximum values. Categorical values are summarized using number of observations and percentages. Withdrawals from the study were summarized by treatment group.

Extent of Exposure

All the randomized patients were exposed to almost similar dosing. The minimum duration of participation of patients in the study was 43 days and maximum duration of participation was 116 days.

Table 15: Extent of Exposure of IP

Treatment Arms	Days of Treatment	Mean Exposure (Days)	Duration of Patient Participation	
			Minimum	Maximum
Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets (Test Product)	Day 112±3	112.20	85	115
Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets (Reference Product)	Day 112±3	111.35	43	116

Patient Exposure: A total of 213 patients were screened in the study out of which 15 patients were screen failure, 06 patients were consent withdrawn before randomization and 192 patients were randomized.

The safety assessment includes information for all 192 randomized patients who were administered the test or reference drug during this study.

Adverse Events (AEs)

Brief Summary of Adverse Events

There were 28 clinical adverse events reported in 28 patients. The adverse events were abdominal pain, arthralgia, asthenia, back pain, constipation, diarrhoea, dizziness, dyspepsia, flatulence, headache, hypoglycemia, nasopharyngitis, nausea, sinusitis and weight gain. All the adverse events were followed up until they were completely resolved. No adverse event led to serious adverse event.

Table 16: AE grouping by System Organ Class

	Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets (N=96)	Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets (N=96)
Nervous system disorders	03 (3.13%)	01 (1.04%)
Gastrointestinal disorders	02 (2.08%)	07 (7.29%)
Infections and infestations	03 (3.13%)	03 (3.13%)
Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders	03 (3.13%)	01 (1.04%)

Metabolism and nutrition disorders	00 (00.00%)	01 (1.04%)
General disorders and administration site conditions	00 (00.00%)	01 (1.04%)
Investigations	02 (2.08%)	01 (1.04%)
Total	13 (13.54%)	15 (15.63%)

Analysis of Adverse Events

Adverse events by time of onset were studied. All clinical adverse events were recorded during course of study. The patients experienced adverse events which include abdominal pain, arthralgia, asthenia, back pain, constipation, diarrhoea, dizziness, dyspepsia, flatulence, headache, hypoglycemia, nasopharyngitis, nausea, sinusitis and weight gain. Total 28 AEs were reported in 28 patients. 13 AEs were reported in Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets arm and 15 AEs were reported in Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets arm. 01 AE from Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets arm and 01 AE from Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets arm were moderate in nature; all the other AEs were mild in nature. All adverse events were followed up until

they were completely resolved. No adverse event led to serious adverse event.

Display of Adverse Events by System Organ Class, Preferred Term and Enrolment Group

Total 28 AEs were reported in 28 patients. 13 AEs were reported in Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets arm and 15 AEs were reported in Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets arm. 01 AE from Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets arm and 01 AE from Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets arm were moderate in nature; all the other AEs were mild in nature.

All adverse events were followed up until they were completely resolved. No adverse event led to serious adverse event. There were no SAEs in the study.

Table 17: Adverse Events by System Organ Class, Preferred Term and Enrollment Group

System Organ Class (SOC) Preferred Term	Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets (N=96)		Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets (N=96)	
	Participants with Event N (%)	Total Events (N)	Participants with Event N (%)	Total Events (N)
Any SOC	13 (13.54%)	13	15 (15.63%)	15
Any Event	13 (13.54%)	13	15 (15.63%)	15
Nervous system disorders	03 (3.13%)	03	01 (1.04%)	01
Headache	02 (2.08%)	02	01 (1.04%)	01
Dizziness	01 (1.04%)	01	00 (00.00%)	00
Gastrointestinal disorders	02 (2.08%)	02	07 (7.29%)	07
Diarrhoea	01 (1.04%)	01	01 (1.04%)	01
Dyspepsia	00 (00.00%)	00	01 (1.04%)	01
Nausea	00 (00.00%)	00	01 (1.04%)	01
Abdominal pain	01 (1.04%)	01	02 (2.08%)	02
Constipation	00 (00.00%)	00	01 (1.04%)	01
Flatulence	00 (00.00%)	00	01 (1.04%)	01
Infections and infestations	03 (3.13%)	03	03 (3.13%)	03
Nasopharyngitis	02 (2.08%)	02	01 (1.04%)	01
Sinusitis	01 (1.04%)	01	02 (2.08%)	02
Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders	03 (3.13%)	03	01 (1.04%)	01
Arthralgia	01 (1.04%)	01	00 (00.00%)	00
Back pain	02 (2.08%)	02	01 (1.04%)	01
Metabolism and nutrition disorders	00 (00.00%)	00	01 (1.04%)	01
Hypoglycaemia	00 (00.00%)	00	01 (1.04%)	01

Table 18: Adverse Events by System Organ Class, Preferred Term and Enrollment Group

System Organ Class (SOC) Preferred Term	Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets (N=96)		Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets (N=96)	
	Participants with Event N (%)	Total Events (N)	Participants with Event N (%)	Total Events (N)
General disorders and administration site	00 (00.00%)	00	01 (1.04%)	01

conditions				
Asthenia	00 (00.00%)	00	01 (1.04%)	01
Investigations	02 (2.08%)	02	01 (1.04%)	01
Weight gain	02 (2.08%)	02	01 (1.04%)	01

Note: Percentages are based on the number of patients in safety population in respective treatment group. System organ class and preferred terms are coded using the MedDRA version 23.0 dictionary.

Other Adverse Events

Adverse events by time of onset were studied. All clinical adverse events were recorded during course of study.

Table 19: Summary of Adverse Events by Enrolment Group

	Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets (N=96)	Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets (N=96)
Number of Events/Participants		
Number of Adverse Events	13 (13.54%)	15 (15.63%)
Participants with at least one AE	13	15
Number of SAEs	00	00
Severity (All AEs)		
Mild	12	14
Moderate	01	01

Table 20: Summary of Adverse Events by Enrolment Group

	Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets (N=96)	Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets (N=96)
Severe	00	00
Relationship		
Related	02	02
Not Related	11	13

Safety Conclusions

For evaluation of safety, frequency of suspected, unanticipated adverse drug reactions reported possibly related to the investigational product up to end of study from start of the treatment was considered. Safety and tolerability of the test and reference products were assessed depending on the outcome from this clinical study. A total of 28 AEs were reported in 28 patients. 13 AEs were reported in Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets arm and 15 AEs were reported in Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets arm. 01 AE from Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets arm and 01 AE Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets arm were moderate in nature; all the other AEs were mild in nature. No SAE was reported during the study.

There were no deaths or hospitalizations in either treatment groups. Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets were found to be safe and well tolerated in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus inadequately controlled on Metformin monotherapy.

Discussion and Overall Conclusion

The study was a phase III, prospective, randomized, double blind, comparative, parallel group clinical study conducted at Maharaja Agrasen Superspeciality Hospital in India. The

study screened 213 male and female patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus inadequately controlled on Metformin monotherapy, out of which 192 patients were randomized by computer generated system to either of the study arms. Thus, 96 patients were randomized in test product i.e., Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets out of which 94 patients completed the study and 96 patients were randomized in reference product i.e., Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets out of which 93 patients completed the study. Site held prior approval from Institutional Ethics Committee for the conduct of the study.

Patient's ICF, demographic data and medical history were taken on screening visit/baseline visit only. After providing informed consent, all subjects were screened as per the screening procedures. During screening procedures,

After screening, patients were advised to return to site and were randomized to the drug treatment. This day was defined as day 1 (Randomization/visit 2) of treatment. Both the investigator and the patient were blinded to the study medication. Patients meeting the eligibility criteria after screening were randomized in the study. On the day of randomization, patients were instructed to administer one tablet orally, swallowed as a whole

with water in the morning after breakfast around same time every day for 16 weeks. During the study, patients were prohibited from using strong CYP2C8 inhibitors (e.g., Gemfibrozil), CYP2C8 inducers (e.g., Rifampin), Topiramate, drugs increasing hypoglycemic action: β -blocking agents, salicylic acid, monoamine oxidase inhibitors, drugs decreasing hypoglycemic action: adrenalin and adrenocortical hormone, drugs known to cause QT prolongation: Class IA antiarrhythmic drug Quinidine sulfate hydrate, Procainamide Hydrochloride, Class III antiarrhythmic drugs Amiodarone Hydrochloride, Sotalol Hydrochloride. Digoxin, Oral hypoglycemic agents other than study medication, weight loss medication, including but not limited to Mazindol, Sibutramine, Phentermine, Orlistat, Rimonabant, Benzphetamine, Diethylpropion, Methamphetamine, and/or Phendimetrazine, oral hormonal contraceptive pills, immunosuppressant medications that are known to increase the risk of infections, medications that are expected to interfere with blood glucose levels including but not limited to loop or potassium sparing diuretics, tricyclic amines, beta-blockers etc. and Potent inducers of CYP3A4, including Rifabutin, Rifampin, Efavirenz, Carbamazepine, Dexamethasone, Barbiturates, Phenytoin and Oxcarbazepine. However, patients were allowed to take other medications at Investigator's discretion if it is required by the patient and not affecting the study outcomes.

The patients were instructed to return to study site on day 14 \pm 3 / visit 3, day 42 \pm 3 / visit 4, day 84 \pm 3 / visit 5 and 112 \pm 3 / visit 6. HbA1c, HbA1c was also performed at visit 5 (week 12 / day 84 \pm 3) and visit 6 (week 16 / day 112 \pm 3). FPG and 2-hour PPG were also performed at day 14 \pm 3 (visit 3), day 42 \pm 3 (visit 4), day 84 \pm 3 (visit 5) and day 112 \pm 3 (visit 6). 12 Lead ECG was also performed at day 42 \pm 3 (visit 4), day 84 \pm 3 (visit 5) and day 112 \pm 3 (visit 6). Routine urine analysis (microscopy) was also performed at day 112 \pm 3 (visit 6). Urine pregnancy test (for females of childbearing potential only) were performed at day 42 \pm 3 (visit 4), day 84 \pm 3 (visit 5) and day 112 \pm 3 (visit 6).

Study drug dispensing was done at visit 2 (day 1), visit 3 (day 14 \pm 3), visit 4 (day 42 \pm 3) and visit 5 (day 84 \pm 3). Patient diary was dispensed at randomization visit/visit 2 (day 1). Drug accountability was performed using patient diary and used/unused strips or study drug bottles at visit 3 (day 14 \pm 3), visit 4 (day 42 \pm 3), visit 5 (day 84 \pm 3) and visit 6 (day 112 \pm 3). Assessment of adverse events and record of concomitant medication were done at all visits. Patients were assigned to either of the study arm by computer generated randomization process. Each patient was provided

with study medication and diary to record the drug treatment compliance and reporting of any specific observations. The data was collected on paper CRF at site. The data analysis was performed for predefined parameters to correspond with the efficacy parameter.

Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets produced statistically significant reductions in glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c), fasting plasma glucose (FPG) and 2-hour post prandial plasma glucose (2-hr PPG) from baseline to end of the study visit. No significant differences were observed between Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets and Teneligliptin 20 mg + Tablets in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus inadequately controlled on Metformin monotherapy.

For evaluation of safety, frequency of suspected, unanticipated adverse drug reactions reported possibly related to the investigational product up to end of study from start of the treatment was considered. Safety and tolerability of the test and reference products were assessed depending on the outcome from this clinical study. A total of 28 AEs were reported in 28 patients. 13 AEs were reported in Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets arm and 15 AEs were reported in Teneligliptin 20 mg + Pioglitazone 15 mg Tablets arm. 01 AE from Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets arm and 01 AE from Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets arm were moderate in nature; all the other AEs were mild in nature.

Inference:

For primary efficacy variable, mean change in glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) from baseline to end of the study visit (16 weeks) in the two groups has been calculated and non-inferiority has been considered when the lower bound of the two-sided 95% CI of the difference between the mean change in glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) at week 16 as compared to baseline (Test product – Reference product) is not less than -0.40.

The glycosylated hemoglobin was decreased in both the treatment groups. The difference in the mean change in glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) at the end of 16 weeks in the two groups was -0.03 with lower limit of 95% CI being -0.18, thereby meeting the requirements of non-inferiority criteria. Thus, the results of the study show that Vildagliptin SR 100 mg Tablets is non-inferior to Teneligliptin 20 mg Tablets.

All the treatments were well tolerated.

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